

D7.6

Second Update Communication and Dissemination Plan

Submission Date 2025.12.11	Version 1.0 – Submitted Version		
	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive	
Due Date 2025.12.31	R-UE/UE-R	EU classified	
Deliverable Title	Second Update Communication and Dissemination Plan		
Deliverable No.	D7.6		
Lead beneficiary	MWS		
Contributing WP	WP7		
Type	R – Document, report		
	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01 Grant Agreement: 101094397		

Project Full Title	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
Project Acronym	CRAFT-OA
Project No.	101094397
Start Date	2023.01.01
End Date	2025.12.31
Duration	36 Months
Project Website	https://craft-oa.eu
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Abstract	This deliverable is an update to CRAFT-OA deliverables 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan and 7.5 First Update Communication and Dissemination Plan. It summarizes and evaluates the project's communication and dissemination measures and highlights specific outreach and community engagement activities.

Version and Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer/Contributors	Comments
0.1	2025.10.20	Author: Kelly Achenbach (MWS)	Initial Draft
0.2	2025.10.22	Author: Léa Foumany (MWS)	Initial Draft
0.3		Contributors: Elena Sokolova (OPERAS); Antti-Jussi Nygard (TSV); Hanna Varachkina (UGOE), Arnaud Gingold (OpenEdition), Marion Paulhac (OPERAS)	Contributors
0.4	2025.11.11	Reviewer: Karl Heyer (UGOE)	External Review
0.5	2025.11.11	Reviewer: Valeria Ardizzone (EGI Foundation)	Internal Review
0.6	2025.11.25	Authors: Kelly Achenbach (MWS); Léa Foumany (MWS)	Final Edit
0.7	2025.12.11	Contributor: Theresa Waldmann	Final formal check
1.0	2025.12.11		Submitted Version

Disclaimer

CRAFT-OA is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101094397. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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List of Acronyms

C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
D	Deliverable
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
Diamond OA	Diamond Open Access
DISCO	Discoverability Companion
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
IPSPs	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
IPTPs	Institutional Publishing Technology and Tool Providers
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
JMEF	Journal Metadata Exchange Format
KER	Key Exploitable Result

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS	Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication
OPS	Open Preprint Systems
PALOMERA	Supporting the Development of Aligned Policies for Open Access Books and Monographs
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
T	Task
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
UGOE	University of Göttingen
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D7.6, “Second Update Communication and Dissemination Plan” provides an overview of CRAFT-OA’s communication, dissemination, and community engagement activities from 2023 to 2025, building on deliverables 7.1 and 7.5. Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access (CRAFT-OA) is a three-year European project (1 January 2023-31 December 2025) funded under Horizon Europe, bringing together 23 partners from 14 countries and coordinated by Georg-August-Universität Göttingen. The project strengthens the Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) publishing landscape by improving technical and organisational infrastructures, fostering communities of practice, enhancing visibility, and integrating with infrastructures like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

At its core, CRAFT-OA promotes Diamond OA, an equitable publishing model in which neither authors nor readers pay fees and scholarly communities control content. Aligned with Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) and related initiatives (e.g., Supporting the Development of Aligned Policies for Open Access Books and Monographs (PALOMERA)) through shared events, co-developed materials, and harmonised methodologies, CRAFT-OA engaged diverse stakeholders to develop and disseminate useful technologies, including Open Journal Systems (OJS) enhancements, Diamond plugins, the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Publisher Dashboard, and the Guide to Scholarly Indexes. The project mapped the community’s technical training needs, consolidated existing training, and filled gaps through in-person and online workshops, webinars, and summer school programmes. It also contributed to mechanisms for community collaboration, such as the Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond OA and the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) Registry & Forum. Coordinating these efforts required aligning messaging across the consortium, external stakeholders, and the broader community.

CRAFT-OA employed a multi-channel outreach strategy including a website, newsletters, social media, Zenodo-hosted resources, 38 project events, and 61 external engagements. Activities included technical workshops, “Coffee Lectures,” “Meet the Experts” webinars, and two summer schools for journal editors, culminating in a final conference in October 2025 with 145 participants from 17 countries.

The project exceeded most communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), achieving over 11,000 Zenodo downloads and broad participation. The deliverable concludes that coordinated messaging, stakeholder co-creation, and cross-initiative alignment were key to building a sustainable, active European Diamond OA ecosystem.

2 INTRODUCTION: DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES

This deliverable complements the two previous deliverables: D7.1, “Communication and Dissemination Plan”¹ submitted in June 2023 and D7.5, “First Update Communication and Dissemination Plan”² submitted in June 2024. The Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy outlined in D7.1 served as a guideline for all C&D efforts in Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access (CRAFT-OA), while D7.5 outlined the adjustments made to the plan and strategy in response to project developments. Deliverable D7.6 documents the actual dissemination efforts and engagement strategies employed during the project, thus updating the numbers reported in D7.5 to include activities that took place between July 2024 and December 2025, and it outlines plans for continuing dissemination efforts related to the project's results beyond its completion. The C&D measures and activities described on the following pages support efforts to exploit and sustain the project's results, as detailed in D7.7, “Update Exploitation and Sustainability Plan”³.

¹ D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112794>

² D7.2 First Update Communication and Dissemination Plan:
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12608032>

³ D7.7 Update Exploitation and Sustainability Plan: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17531325>

3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION: SUMMARY

This chapter is organised into three sections. Section 2.1 briefly describes the internal and external communication channels and how they were utilised throughout the project. Section 2.2 summarises the events that CRAFT-OA project partners organised for the community and the external events where CRAFT-OA partners engaged with the community. Finally, community engagement activities specific to each CRAFT-OA Key Exploitable Result (KER) are described in section 2.3.

Throughout the project, the C&D objectives were to:

- Inform stakeholders about the project's progress, development, and results
- Create awareness for the Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) publishing model
- Support the sustainability and exploitation of the project results
- Promote the project's results and ensure their visibility, accessibility, and availability
- Engage the Open Access (OA) community, thereby contributing to the creation and consolidation of a "community of practice"
- Guarantee a continuous flow of information among the consortium members

CRAFT-OA project's C&D activities were carried out in four phases:

1. Phase 1: Launching activities and engaging with stakeholders
2. Phase 2: Informing and updating on ongoing activities
3. Phase 3: Disseminating final outputs
4. Phase 4: Maintain the project's results beyond funding

Figure 1: Communication and Dissemination Phases

3.1 Communication Channels and Usage

Website

The project website, craft-oa.eu, was continually updated throughout the project to communicate and document all aspects of the project, from its original plans to the final results. Over the three years, 17 blog posts were published on the website to describe various CRAFT-OA events or delve deeper into the details of the project results. Each of the project's six⁴ KERs has its own dedicated page, prominently featuring a 5-8 minute video that explains the result in detail. All project deliverables and recordings are linked on the website. The website will be available through 2030 as a resource for the community.

⁴ In deliverable 7.5, five KERs were discussed; an additional KER was added to the project after that report was published.

Emails lists

The project coordination team managed several internal and external email lists. The three lists used for general communication purposes were: 1) the CRAFT-OA project member list (116⁵ subscribers); 2) a list populated by a survey distributed by Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) (353 subscribers) where survey participants could opt-in to receive updates on the DIAMAS project; and 3) the CRAFT-OA newsletter list (758 subscribers), which anyone could subscribe to directly from the project website. The first two email lists were used to inform the community about upcoming events or initiatives organised by CRAFT-OA and the Diamond OA community at large. The newsletter list, as its name suggests, was used to send CRAFT-OA newsletters.

Newsletter

Between June 2023 and December 2025, 14 newsletters were sent via the newsletter email list. The content of the newsletters was curated by the communication task leader, with input from the CRAFT-OA work package leaders, and focused on CRAFT-OA-led events and results. It also included news from related initiatives and the wider Diamond OA community.

Zenodo

All of CRAFT-OA deliverables are published in a dedicated Zenodo community⁶ along with related publications (non-deliverables) from within the CRAFT-OA project and other initiatives. CRAFT-OA established two additional Zenodo communities: the “2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors 2025”⁷ and the “CRAFT-OA Conference October 6-8 2025”⁸. Materials were uploaded to these communities to ensure continued access to slides and educational materials critical for Diamond OA publishing. Overall, publications from the CRAFT-OA Zenodo community were downloaded 11,914⁹ times, far exceeding the original goal of 1,000 downloads.

Social Media

In 2023, CRAFT-OA established a presence on X and Mastodon. In December 2024, CRAFT-OA discontinued using X (but did not delete the account), following the shift of many project partners and community members, and began using BlueSky. The table below lists the number of followers and posts for each account as of November 5,

⁵ The number of email addresses reported in this sentence were accurate on November 5, 2025.

⁶ CRAFT-OA Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oa/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oasummerschool/> The materials from the second summer school updated the materials from the first summer school, which is why there is only one related Zenodo community.

⁸ https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oa_conference/

⁹ The download number reported here was accurate on November 10, 2025.

2025. Posts on CRAFT-OA social media accounts focused on the project events and results. Efforts were made to repost, like, and comment on posts from project partners and the global Diamond OA community.

Social media account	# followers	#posts ¹⁰
X (@craftoa_project)	485	280
Mastodon (@craftoa)	224	224
BlueSky (@craft-oa.bsky.social)	332	77

Table 1: CRAFT-OA Social Media statistics

3.2 Community Events

Organised by CRAFT-OA

Throughout the project, CRAFT-OA members organised 25 online and 13 in-person events to support the co-creation and dissemination of project results. These included various technical workshops/webinars/trainings, two week-long summer school sessions for journal editors, consortium meetings for project reflection and coordination, an in-person Public Knowledge Project (PKP) Sprint/Tech event, and the project's final conference to engage with and facilitate exchange among the Diamond OA community. Whenever possible, recordings were made and added to a [dedicated page](#) of the CRAFT-OA website.

A few highlights:

- The three-part event “Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable, Open Scholarly Publishing”, which took place in June 2023, February 2024 and November 2024, was a collaborative effort between the CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS, and Supporting the Development of Aligned Policies for Open Access Books and Monographs (PALOMERA) projects to communicate with each other and the broader Diamond OA community about the various actions being taken by the different projects, each of which addressed different aspects to build Diamond OA publishing capacities.
- In October 2025 (Turin, Italy), CRAFT-OA hosted two back-to-back in-person events. First, the PKP Sprint brought together journal managers, librarians, programmers, and user interface experts to enhance open-source publishing platforms, including Open Journal Systems (OJS), Open Monograph Press (OMP), and Open Preprint Systems (OPS). The Sprint was followed by a gathering titled “CRAFT-OA Tech Event: Advancing Technology for Diamond Open Access”¹¹, which featured presentations, workshops, and discussions related to innovative technologies shaping Diamond OA publishing.

¹⁰ These numbers were accurate on November 20, 2025.

¹¹ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/pkp-sprint-tech-event/>

- In June 2024¹² (Telč, Czech Republic) and June 2025¹³ (Coimbra, Portugal), CRAFT-OA hosted no-cost one-week summer school opportunities for journal editors. Workshops introduced participants to essential topics related to Diamond OA journals, such as Extensible Markup Language (XML) workflows and the OJS plugins developed by CRAFT-OA, as well as other outputs developed within the CRAFT-OA project.
- CRAFT-OA organised six online Coffee Lectures¹⁴, spanning across 7 months, to explain and promote technical publication standards for Diamond OA publishing.
- In the fall of 2025, CRAFT-OA hosted five “Meet the Experts” webinars to provide practical support to OJS users on installing, upgrading, and configuring Open Journal Systems (OJS).
- CRAFT-OA’s final conference, “Crafting the Future of Diamond Open Access: Technical, Social & Political Perspectives of Scholarly Publishing”, a three-day event in October 2025, gathered 145 participants from 17 countries. It included 52 talks and sessions, 28 posters, and an expert panel discussion. Results from the CRAFT-OA project were presented at various plenary sessions and promoted through printed materials, such as stickers, brochures, and drink coasters. The conference was co-branded with the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) logo to demonstrate the direct connection between the two to the community. Additionally, all Diamond OA National Capacity Centre (NCC) representatives from across Europe were explicitly invited to the event. The EDCH convened a dedicated meeting with these representatives to develop connections further and establish a collaborative agenda.

2025	Event	Event Type	Location	No. Participants
6-8 Oct	CRAFT-OA Consortium Meeting	Consortium Meeting	Göttingen, Germany	44
6-8 Oct	CRAFT-OA Final Event	Conference	Göttingen, Germany	137
26 Sep	CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture on Training Material created at IBL PAN	Webinar	Online	19
23-27 Jun	2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School	Training	Coimbra, Portugal	51
12 Jun	CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture on GDPR issues and development in OJS	Webinar	Online	20
5 June	CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture on Self-Archiving Policies	Webinar	Online	12

¹² <https://www.craft-oa.eu/report-summer-school-2024/>

¹³ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/enabling-diamond-oa-insights-from-the-2nd-craft-oa-summer-school/>

¹⁴ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/coffee-lectures-1/>

3 Jun	Diamond Open Access: Auf Schatzsuche mit CRAFT-OA und der EZB	Training	Online	159
7 May	Diamond Open Access: Auf Schatzsuche mit CRAFT-OA und der EZB	Training	Online	120
1 Apr	CRAFT-OA webinar in collaboration with Crossref: "Metadata Introduction and Metadata Healthcheck"	Webinar	Online	34
5 Mar	CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture on OJS journal set up	Webinar	Online	20
20 Feb	Creating JATS XML from DOCX documents on HRČAK	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	n/a
10 Feb	CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture on OpenAIRE Guidelines	Webinar	Online	34

2024	Event	Event Type	Location	No. Participants
12 Dec	CRAFT-OA Webinar "OpenAIRE Graph Part 2: OpenAIRE Services"	Webinar	Online	28
9 Dec	CRAFT-OA Webinar "OpenAIRE Graph Part 1: EOSC & EOSC EU Node"	Webinar	Online	41
26 Nov	Coffee Lecture "Wie nutze ich DOI, ROR und ORCID?"	Webinar	Online	20
6 Nov	Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable, Open Scholarly Publishing With DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, PALOMERA), 3rd webinar	Webinar	Online	n/a
30 Oct	OJS: Experiences and Recommendations	Workshop	Online	211
24 Oct	Refining Croatian journals for a Diamond Open Access future	Webinar	online	48
9-12 Oct	IPTP technical event	Workshop	Turin, Italy	n/a
8-9 Oct	PKP Sprint	Workshop	Turin, Italy	n/a
27 Sept	Creating JATS XML from	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	8

	DOCX documents on HRČAK			
18-20 Jun	General Assembly	Consortium Meeting	Helsinki, Finland	n/a
27 May-2 Jun	Summer School (MU)	Training	Telc, Czech Republic	39
23 May	Creating JATS XML from DOCX documents on HRČAK	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	8
16 May	Shaping Diamond OA: Criteria for Journals	Webinar, Community Consultation	Online	111
18 Apr	Advanced usage of OJS for journal editors	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	n/a
22 Mar	Creating JATS XML from DOCX documents on HRČAK	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	11
27 Feb	Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable, Open Scholarly Publishing With DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, PALOMERA), 2nd webinar	Webinar	Online	112
26 Jan	Creating JATS XML from DOCX documents on HRČAK	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	13

2023	Event	Event Type	Location	No. Participants
8 Dec	Creating JATS XML from DOCX documents on HRČAK	Workshop	Zagreb, Croatia	13
23-24 Nov	FitSM Foundation Training	Training	Online	13
23 Nov	Authentication and Authorization	Workshop	Online	13
6-7 Nov	FitSM Foundation Training	Training	Online	12
20 Jun	"Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable, Open Scholarly Publishing With DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, PALOMERA), 1st webinar	Webinar	Online	190

21-23 Mar	CRAFT-OA Kick off	Consortium Meeting	Göttingen, Germany	n/a
26-27 Jan	Kick-off (online)	Consortium Meeting	Online	n/a

Table 2: Events organised by CRAFT-OA

CRAFT-OA represented at external events

CRAFT-OA team members participated in events such as conferences and workshops to inform and engage the project's stakeholders in its initiatives. Contributions to these events varied and included informative posters, interactive workshops, panel and roundtable participation, session facilitation, and formal presentations.

As of November 2025, consortium members have represented the project at 62 external events listed below.

2025	Event	Event Type	Location	Contribution
21 Nov	Infoclio.ch Conference 2025	Conference	Bern, Switzerland	Timeline Poster
18-20 Nov	MUNIN 2025	Conference	Tromsø, Norway	Poster, workshop. Presentation
10-14 Nov	OAI14 Conference	Conference	online	Facilitation
6-7 Nov	NWM-Jahrestagung 2025	Conference	Haale, Germany	Other
25 Sept	Abbracciare il futuro: fare Scienza Aperta oggi/Embrace the future: do Open Science today	Conference	hybrid	Roundtable
17-19 Sept	Open Access Tage 2025	Conference	Konstanz, Germany	Presentation
15-17 Sept	Open Science Fair	Conference	Geneva, Switzerland	Workshop
11-12 Sept	PUBMET 2025	Conference	Zagreb, Croatia	Poster, Presentation
3 Sept	OJS and OMP Publishers' theme day	Workshop	Helsinki, Finland	Presentation
2-4 July	Liber conference	Conference	Lausanne, Switzerland	Presentation, Poster
30 Jun-1 July	SeDOA Kick-off (German Capacity Center)	Consortium Meeting	Berlin, Germany	
24-27 June	BiblioCon	Conference	Bremen, Germany	Presentation
3 June	DIAMAS final conference	Conference	Brussels, Belgium	Poster
2-6 June	EGI Conference 2025	Conference	Santander, Spain	Presentation, Poster

2-3 June	PKP Sprint Oslo	Conference	Oslo, Norway	Other
28 May	OJS: Best Practices and Use Cases	Webinar	online	Presentation
22-24 May	2025 4th AEUP Conference	Conference	Vienna, Austria	Presentation
7-9 May	Joint PISA 2025 Conference	Conference	Pisa, Italy	Poster
2-4 Apr	Annual Conference of the Working Group of the German speaking University Presses	Conference	Tübingen Germany	Presentation and Q&A
21 March	Diamond Open Access Workshop Day	workshops	Bern, Switzerland	Workshop
13 March	Open Science café on Diamond OA	Webinar	Online	Other
20-23 Jan	EOOSC winter school	Workshops	Seville, Spain	workshop
15 Jan	EDCH Public Launch	Conference	Madrid, Spain	Presentation
14 Jan	ALMASI Public Launch	Conference	Madrid, Spain	
13-14 Jan	ALMASI Internal Kick-Off	Consortium Meeting	Madrid, Spain	
2024	Event	Event Type	Location	Contribution
26-28 Nov	Munin Conference	Conference	Tromsø, Norway	Workshop
19 Nov	IFLA Publishing SIG: Empowering Communities. CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS & PALOMERA	Webinar	online	Presentation
24 Oct	Open Access week: webinar "Refining Croatian journals for a Diamond Open Access future"	Webinar	online	Presentation
16-18 Sept	OASPA Conference	Conference	Lisbon, Portugal	Panel Discussion
11-13 Sept	PUBMET 2024	Conference	Zadar, Croatia	Presentation
10-12 Sept	Open Access Tage 2024	Conference	Cologne, Germany	Workshop, Presentation, Poster
3-5 July	LIBER Annual Conference	Conference	Limassol, Cyprus	Workshop
20-21 Jun	Coordination Meeting of EOOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe	Workshop	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation
4-7 Jun	BiblioCon 24	Conference	Hamburg, Germany	Presentation
29-31 May	GARR conference 2024	Conference	Brescia, Italy	Presentation
7 May	Research Infrastructure and European Open Science Cloud in the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructure Work Programme	Symposium	Madrid, Spain	Presentation

24-16 Apr	OPERAS Conference 2024	Conference	Zadar, Croatia	Workshop, Presentation
16-18 Apr	SCRE DEI 2024 Conference	Conference	Zagreb, Croatia	Poster
11-12 Apr	Annual Conference of the Working Group of the German speaking University Presses	Conference	Bozen, Italy	Presentation
8 Mar	Acting together for Sustainable Scholar-Led Publishing. National Diamond Open Access Conference	Conference	Bern, Switzerland	Presentations, Panel Discussion
6 Feb	Open Access Publishing in FAIR Action Plans	Workshop	Online	Presentation
29 Jan-2 Feb	EOSC Winter School	Workshop	Thessaloniki, Greece	Other
2023	Event	Event Type	Location	Contribution
23 Nov	Digitales Anwenderforum	Webinar	Online	Presentation
23-26 Oct	Global Summit on Diamond Open Access	Conference	Toluca, Mexico	Presentation, Poster
26 Oct	Advancing Research Visibility through National Portals – Insights from spearheading institutions	Other	Online	Panel discussion
23-27 Oct	Intern. OA Week	Other	Online	Presentation
23-27 Oct	GenOA Week	Other	Genova, Italy	Presentation
9-10 Oct	Digital Total	Conference	Hamburg, Germany	Poster
27-29 Sep	Open Access Tage Berlin	Conference	Berlin, Germany	Presentation
25-27 Sep	Open Science Fair	Conference	Madrid, Spain	Poster
21 Sep	Danish Research Library Association	Conference	Horsens, Denmark	Presentation
13-15 Sep	PUBMET2023	Conference	Zadar, Croatia	Poster
11-13 Sep	PKP Sprint	Other	Hannover, Germany	Other
5 Sep	OPERAS-GER “Connecting the Connections”	Conference	Bonn, Germany	Presentation
8-10 Sep	OAI	Conference	Online	Poster
20-21 Jun	PKP Sprint	Other	Copenhagen, Denmark	Other
19-23 Jun	EGI2023	Conference	Poznań, Poland	Networking
15 Jun	OPERAS Ger Open Chat	Open Chat	Online	Q & A Session

15 Jun	AUP Annual Meeting	Conference	Online	Panel Discussion
23-26 May	BiblioCon	Conference	Hannover, Germany	Presentation
16-17 May	AEUP Conference	Conference	Tallinn & Tartu, Estonia	Other
28-30 Mar	SRCE DEI 2023 conference	Conference	Zagreb, Croatia	Poster

Table 3: CRAFT-OA external event participation

3.3 Community Engagement: CRAFT-OA KERs and EDCH

This section highlights the specific actions, already taken and planned for the future, to engage the Diamond OA community during and after the development of each KER. Additionally, it covers the EDCH's role in maintaining community engagement beyond the project's end.

Six CRAFT-OA results, described briefly in the following section, were identified as KERs, and special efforts were made to engage the community with them. Deliverable D7.2, "Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination", included an analysis concerning the exploitation and sustainability of five of these KERs. During the second reporting period, an additional KER (KER6) was introduced, and several titles were adjusted to reflect their actual nature and application better. The final set of six KERs reflects technical, organisational and knowledge layers of Diamond OA publishing. Deliverable D7.5, "Second Update on Communication and Dissemination Plan", addressed the specific communication strategies for each KER by identifying the key values and key messages with respect to the targeted stakeholder groups. It is important to note that the KERs were not only built with and for the community: they "live" within and are "nourished" by the community, as explained in D7.7, "Update Exploitation and Sustainability Plan".

In the final project phase, it was essential to communicate CRAFT-OA's KERs to a broad audience and to reach as many and as diverse stakeholders as possible. Therefore, each KER was presented on the project website with its own dedicated page containing a detailed description and direct links to the actual products. Building on the methodology described in D7.5, CRAFT-OA adopted a framework structured around a KER-driven model: each result is assigned to a responsible project member, a designated "Champion", who tracked all aspects of its development and dissemination.

To strengthen the visibility and coherence of the CRAFT-OA KERs at the CRAFT-OA Conference (6-8 October 2025), a unified visual identity was created for all six. Each KER presentation at the conference was highlighted in the conference programme and assigned its own colour and design, while maintaining a consistent overall visual concept. Following the event, the presentation slides were uploaded to the Zenodo community, where the KERs were made particularly visible and accessible.

Figure 2: Photos of printed coasters at the CRAFT-OA conference (@Martin Liebethuth) (image 2 and 3) and screenshots from KER presentation recording to show the streamlined KER visuals (image 1 and 4).

KER1: Diamond Discovery Hub

Description: The Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) is a registry of Diamond OA journals in Europe, providing verified, structured information to ensure their visibility, discoverability, and recognition. As a dynamic and evolving data collection, the DDH focuses on different stakeholder groups at various stages – starting with data providers and gradually involving publishers, libraries, and researchers. After its beta release at the end of June 2025, the official launch took place on 7 October 2025 during CRAFT-OA’s final conference. The DDH is conceptualised as one of the key services of the EDCH, supporting a sustainable and collaborative Diamond OA ecosystem in Europe.

C&D activities conducted: Diamond OA journal editors and staff, journal service providers, researchers, and librarians were engaged at external events throughout the project, including the Open Access Tage (2024, 2025), the CRAFT-OA Tech event (2024), the DIAMAS final conference (2025), PUBMET¹⁵ (2025), and the MUNIN Conference (2024¹⁶, 2025¹⁷). Additional activities included webinars, such as “Refining Croatian Journals for a Diamond Open Access Future”¹⁸ (2024), as well as

¹⁵ Poster: <https://www.craft-oa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/70-x-100-PUBMET-1.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.7557/5.7810>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.7557/5.8247>

¹⁸ <https://repozitorij.srce.unizg.hr/islandora/object/srce%3A871>

workshops and presentations at CRAFT-OA-organised events, including the CRAFT-OA Tech Event (2024), the CRAFT-OA Second Summer School (June 2025), and the CRAFT-OA conference (2025).

In preparation for the official launch of the DDH in October 2025, a coherent visual design and several dissemination materials were produced, including merchandise items (reflective gear and stickers), an animated video explaining the DDH (embedded on the Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication (OPERAS) YouTube channel and the CRAFT-OA website), and a three-fold printed flyer.

Communication efforts were further supported through the newsletter, the EDCH forum, social media, and the project website. Social media announcements were coordinated with the EDCH social media channels. Several blog posts were

Figure 3: Selection of DDH visuals - 3-fold (image 1), screenshot from introduction video (image 2), and visual diagram of the six criteria for Diamond OA journals (image 3).

published about the DDH – notably on the CRAFT-OA Blog, “Behind the Scenes: “Verifying Journals in DOAJ for the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)”¹⁹ (June 2025), as well as on the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) Blog, “DOAJ and the Diamond Discovery Hub: Working with the Community to Support Open Access”²⁰ (October 2025).

¹⁹ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/ddh-verifying-journals/>

²⁰ <https://blog.doaj.org/2025/10/23/doaj-and-the-diamond-discovery-hub-working-with-the-community-to-support-open-access/>

C&D activities planned: As a dynamic data collection, the DDH will continue to grow over time and will be sustained and expanded through several partners, including the EDCH, the DOAJ, and the Georg-August-Universität (UGOE). Communication to the public about the DDH will be managed through the EDCH using the visual and communication materials developed within the CRAFT-OA project. This material was developed in collaboration with the EDCH community manager during the last phase of the project. The EDCH has actively promoted the DDH through all its communication channels since its official launch in October 2025. Additionally, the EDCH supports the Trusted Source applications, which begin through a process on the EDCH Forum. Once approved through the UGOE, DDH Trusted Sources are added to a special mailing list and group in the EDCH Forum, where they share their Diamond and DDH expertise with each other. They are encouraged to help disseminate information about the DDH and strengthen engagement within their communities.

KER2: OJS Core Feature Enhancements

Description: This set of core improvements to Open Journal Systems (OJS) addresses multilingual metadata, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, and data export standards to align OJS with European interoperability and accessibility requirements. The enhanced core features include implementing new solutions that enable editors to work with user and reviewer data in a GDPR-compliant manner, as well as addressing identified shortcomings in the platform's support for multilingual content and metadata. Additionally, the capability to interact with diverse controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, and persistent identifiers is enhanced, accompanied by the introduction of automated metadata checks, thereby contributing to an improved standard of metadata quality. OJS, developed by the PKP and the community around it, is the single most used journal management system. The KER will therefore have a significant impact on the European and global Diamond OA publishing landscape. The new features will be incorporated into future releases of OJSs and will be available for OMP (for publishing books) and OPS (for publishing preprints). The functions developed will become an integral part of the software and will be maintained and further developed by the PKP community after the end of the project.

The communication of this KER mainly targeted Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs), the developer community, and the journal editors responsible for single Diamond OA journals. The work may also be of interest to the broader community working with Diamond OA journals.

C&D activities conducted: The KER2 was communicated through workshops and presentations during several events, including the CRAFT-OA Technical Event (October 2024), the PKP Sprint (October 2024 and June 2025), the OJS and OMP Publishers Theme Day (2025), and the CRAFT-OA conference (2025). Communication activities also included the publication of two CRAFT-OA blog posts targeting IPSPs, journal editors, IPSPs and developers: "CRAFT-OA brings multilingual improvements to Open Journal Systems 3.5"²¹ and a post on how CRAFT-OA work is visible in OJS

²¹ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/craft-oa-brings-multilingual-improvements-to-open-journal-systems-3-5/>

3.6²² (forthcoming). Furthermore, CRAFT-OA coordinated with the PKP communication team to promote the “CRAFT-OA Meet the Experts online workshop series”²³, which were designed to inform and engage the community about the improvements, through social media and email campaigns.

C&D activities planned: As OJS is a living platform that is continually updated, PKP has a communication team that constantly engages with its community of users through blog posts and social media, and gives credit to CRAFT-OA where appropriate (they have posted a combined 21 blog posts and news items²⁴ mentioning CRAFT-OA’s work). PKP will continue these practices to inform the community about all OJS improvements in its upcoming 3.6 version, which also includes work completed within the CRAFT-OA project.

KER3: OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard

Description: The Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Publisher Dashboard is a data-driven component of the OpenAIRE MONITOR service, tailored to support Diamond OA publishers. Built within the OpenAIRE MONITOR and powered by the OpenAIRE Graph, it provides publishers with a set of curated, community-driven indicators, offering a consolidated and transparent view of their publishing activities and impact. In addition to the main publisher dashboard, the service supports individual dashboards for each journal, enabling more granular tracking and self-monitoring of scholarly production. The Publisher Dashboard provides a suite of metrics and indicators designed to offer Diamond OA publishers actionable insights into their publishing activities and impact.

C&D activities conducted: As the Publisher Dashboard was due to be completed in December 2025, focused communication about it began in the fall of 2025, starting with a call for journals to become “pilots” to test and provide feedback on various aspects of the Publisher Dashboard. This call was executed in collaboration with the EDCH, making use of its established Forum. This ensured a broad dissemination of the call and created awareness of the upcoming product. Additionally, formal in-person presentations about the Publisher Dashboard were given at PUBMET²⁵ (September 2025), at the Open Science Fair (September 2025), and at the CRAFT-OA conference (October 2025). It was also presented within a “CRAFT-OA Coffee Lecture” in February 2025 and at a joint webinar with the GraspOS project and the DIAMAS project in May 2025: “Research Assessment in Transition: Open Infrastructures, Policy, and Diamond Open Access”.²⁶ The Publisher Dashboard’s corresponding OJS Plugin is registered on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Beyond platform²⁷.

C&D activities planned: During the final months of the CRAFT-OA project, a reminder call for pilots was announced and promoted through the EDCH forum, the CRAFT-OA

²² To be published December 2025.

²³ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/meet-the-experts/>

²⁴ <https://pkp.sfu.ca/?s=CRAFT-OA>

²⁵ <https://pubmet2025.unizd.hr/pispiringas-abstract/>

²⁶ <https://youtu.be/JeAlhCxG88k?si=pxKkvr4QjzNv8WpL&t=2072>

²⁷ <https://search.marketplace.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/adapters/21.15133%2FZvXqIW>

newsletter and email lists, as well as through social media channels. OpenAIRE owns the product and will add it to its communication plan moving forward. The OpenAIRE officers will work directly with the EDCH to coordinate cross-posting whenever possible.

KER4: Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access

Description: The “Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access” (short version: “Living Handbook”) provides comprehensive information, standards, tools, and training materials for institutional publishing in Diamond OA, offering clear explanations of Diamond OA concepts and technical solutions for Diamond OA publishing. Developed in collaboration with the Diamond OA community, the content is highly relevant and directly applicable. The Living Handbook promotes the dissemination of CRAFT-OA results, the exchange of knowledge, and the sustainable availability of information. “Living” implies the handbook will be regularly updated through continuous editing by community members.

C&D activities conducted: The concept of the Living Handbook was explained at the CRAFT-OA Tech Event (October 2024); the first version was presented at the Second CRAFT-OA Summer School (2025) and at the CRAFT-OA conference (2025). Because the Living Handbook was designed to be integrated into the EDCH, the EDCH team worked closely with the responsible CRAFT-OA project members. This ensures that the EDCH team has a comprehensive understanding of the product and is well-prepared to explain its relevance to the community.

C&D activities planned: The EDCH's commitment to promoting the Living Handbook has already been demonstrated through a side meeting organised by the EDCH for the Diamond OA NCC representatives during the CRAFT-OA conference. There, the EDCH facilitated a discussion on NCC representatives serving as the editorial board for the Living Handbook. Although the precise governance model and editorial workflow have not yet been determined, this collaboration ensures that the Living Handbook is visible across national communities. Furthermore, to increase visibility and access to the community, the Living Handbook will be embedded within the EDCH domain environment.

KER5: OJS diamond plugins

Description: Six OJS Diamond Plugins were developed to support Diamond OA journal editors. According to the OA Diamond Journals Study²⁸, many journal editors manage their journals as a “second job” alongside their primary roles, often as researchers. The plugins enhance interoperability, streamline metadata exchange, and facilitate connections between journals and various aggregators. In short, these plugins make journals more visible and editors’ daily work more manageable. The plugins are openly available on GitHub.

²⁸ Bosman, J., Frantsovåg, J.-E., Kramer, B., Langlais, P.-C. & Proudman, V. (2021): OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4558703>

1. [OJS connector for OpenAIRE Graph](#): plugin for exporting publication metadata according to the OpenAIRE guidelines
2. OJS plugin for the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing: implementation of SWORD v3.0 to OJS (in progress)
3. [OJS plugin for the integration of the OpenAIRE Broker](#): connecting OJS with OpenAIRE's scholarly graph, enriching OJS records with missing metadata
4. [OJS Discoverability Companion \(DISCO\)](#): The DISCO plugin visually indicates which requirements overlap across major indexing databases and aggregators, helping editors streamline their compliance efforts and thus ensuring more visibility for their journal
5. [OJS plugins to enable JATS XML-based interoperability between OJS and Lodel](#): conversion, in both directions, between Commons Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) (used on OpenEdition platforms) and Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS) (used on OJS platforms)
6. [OJS JMEF plugin](#): this plugin extends OJS journal's metadata in compliance with an open format for sharing the journal metadata (Journal Metadata Exchange Format).

C&D activities conducted: Communication about the plugins was directed toward journal editors, journal platforms, and aggregators. Formal presentations of the plugins were held at the CRAFT-OA Tech Event (October 2024), during an EIFL webinar on OJS in May 2025, during the Second CRAFT-OA Summer School 2025 (June), at the DIAMAS final conference in June 2025 (poster), at the PUBMET 2025 (September) conference, and at the MUNIN 2025 (November) conference. PKP has published a number of blog posts and social media updates referencing CRAFT-OA's work on the plugins and a blog post in October 2025, "Who owns our knowledge? How communities power the future of open publishing with PKP"²⁹, which highlights the plugins explicitly.

C&D activities planned: There is ongoing discussion about whether the plugins can be added to the PKP gallery to increase their visibility. The KER5 Champion will continue to present the plugins at relevant events, and the Plugins will be promoted through the dedicated EDCH Forum group. Additionally, a new project is being planned involving several CRAFT-OA project partners to develop an OJS Diamond OA package, which would allow journals to download a version of OJS with all plugins pre-installed.

KER6: Guide to Scholarly Indexes

The Guide to Scholarly Indexes is a collection of structured and synthesized documentation about academic publication indexes. The Guide records detailed information about the indexes' main characteristics, with a particular focus on their data and metadata collection process and requirements. When available, the Guide also provides links to the more exhaustive documentation on the indexes' websites. The data in the Guide is also used to inform the OJS DISCO plugin.

²⁹ <https://pkp.sfu.ca/2025/10/16/open-access-week-2025/>

C&D activities conducted: The Guide was presented at the CRAFT-OA Tech event (Oct 2024), at the Second CRAFT-OA Summer School (June 2025), and at the CRAFT-OA conference (October 2025). Additionally, the Guide has a dedicated “category” within the EDCH Forum, where the community was consulted regarding the design and display, as well as the need for new indexes to be added.

C&D activities planned: The Guide to Scholarly Indexes, like all CRAFT-OA results, is included in the Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond OA, and will benefit from the planned communication actions through the EDCH for it. Additionally, the training conducted at the 2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School will be updated by the end of the project, and Open Edition (the responsible CRAFT-OA partner) will communicate about this updated resource in 2026.

EDCH to sustain CRAFT-OA results

The “IPTP and IPSP networks”, as explained in D7.5, evolved to be the EDCH Registry and Forum. The Registry is a directory offering up-to-date information on publishers, service providers, and tools and technology providers involved in Diamond OA publishing within the European Research Area. The Forum provides an interactive platform for individuals active or interested in Diamond OA to exchange practices, discuss challenges, and strengthen collaboration across Europe. Although the Registry was prepopulated with data on organisations, the organisations themselves verified and published their entry, ensuring accuracy and ownership. The Forum, conversely, was built entirely through community participation, without prepopulated users.

As soon as the Registry and Forum were officially launched, a communication campaign was initiated, including targeted emails to the IPTP and IPSP networks, webinars to introduce them, and community-led discussions on the Forum facilitated by the EDCH Community Task Force to engage with the community and encourage exchange. Beginning with the first introductory webinar, CRAFT-OA used all its communication channels to: 1) consistently inform the Diamond OA community about the EDCH’s presence and aims; 2) encourage people to sign up for the Forum; 3) encourage organisations to register in the Registry; and 4) encourage the community to follow the EDCH social media channels. At the time of writing, the EDCH has 244³⁰ Forum members, and 195³¹ organisations are published on the Registry.

In the last months of the CRAFT-OA project, messages about the impending end of the project and the importance of staying connected with the European Diamond OA community through the EDCH were sent multiple times across all CRAFT-OA communication channels. At the same time, the EDCH established itself through social media presentations and at relevant events, including the CRAFT-OA 2nd Summer School (June 2025) and the CRAFT-OA final conference (Oct 2025). Furthermore, the EDCH, as an OPERAS programme, also benefits from visibility

³⁰ Up-to-date numbers available here: <https://forum.diamas.org/about>

³¹ Up-to-date numbers available here: <https://registry.diamas.org/organisations-map>

through its network, which conducted complementary promotional efforts across its social media and national nodes.

Looking ahead, the EDCH has multiple long-term funding sources with full-time staff devoted to community management and communication. All CRAFT-OA results have been fully integrated into the EDCH website and communication ecosystem, ensuring their continued visibility and uptake within the Diamond OA community.

3.4 Key Performance Indicator Table

The first version of the communication Key Performance Indicator (KPI) table was introduced in D7.1, “Communication and Dissemination Plan” and updated in D7.5. The final version is below, preceded by some explanatory notes. Some of the numbers have already been provided above in relevant sections.

Explanatory notes:

- Communication of Project Results: CRAFT-OA organised 38 events and was represented at an additional 61 external events. Total: 99 events. The 38 events organised by CRAFT-OA had an average of 61 participants. The number of training sessions listed includes the two CRAFT-OA Summer Schools, each a week full of trainings. The 2nd Summer School, for example, comprised 19 training sessions; however, the overall event is counted as one training. The total number also includes events that are not explicitly categorized in the table of events (above) as “trainings”, but were in fact a type of training (for example, *Meet the Experts* workshops and the *CRAFT-OA Coffee Lectures*).
- As of 21 November 2025, 195 organisations were registered in the EDCH Registry. Of the 195 organisations, all are categorised as “Tools and/or Technology Providers”, which is the EDCH categorisation for IPTPs. In addition to the 195 organisations in the EDCH Registry, 244 individuals are registered in the EDCH Forum, representing 210 organisations. Together, the EDCH Registry and Forum represent about 354³² different organisations.

Action	Related KPIs	Target		M36
Communication of Project Results	#events	25 events with partners attending	Updated: 50 events with partners attending	99
	#participants	50 participants per event	Updated: 25 participants on average	61

³² This is only an estimate due to likely errors caused by spelling differences in the data.

	#organisations reached	100 participants at final conference			145
	#training sessions at outreach events	10 training sessions			36
Outreach & communication of the project's concept & opportunities to engage with main target groups	#subscribers to project mailing list	700			758
	#IPTPs in IPTP/IPSP network	600			195
Communication of project outcomes and results	# clicks and downloads via a Zenodo community	1000 downloads from Zenodo			11,914 ³³
	# blog posts through other channels	5 blog posts			21
	#scientific publications	12 scientific publications	Updated: 8 scientific publications		6
Social Media		M18	M24	M36	Final #s
	# X Followers	350	500	600	485
	# X Posts	100	200	450	280
	# Mastodon Followers	50	70	120	225
	# Mastodon Posts	30	60	100	224
	# BlueSky Followers	n/a	n/a	n/a	337
	#BlueSky Posts	n/a	n/a	n/a	77

Table 4: KPI table updated, M36

³³ Accurate on November 10, 2025.

4 FINAL THOUGHTS

CRAFT-OA demonstrated that building a sustainable Diamond OA ecosystem requires more than technical solutions; it relies on coordinated communication, stakeholder co-creation, and alignment across initiatives. To reach individual national audiences, it is essential to consult multiple contacts to determine the most effective channels. Email lists and newsletters are widely used in the community, and it is crucial to establish contacts with individuals who have permission to send messages to the lists and add information to newsletters. Finally, integrating project activities with broader European Open Science initiatives, such as the EDCH, helped reach a wider audience, amplifying impact and ensuring that tools, training, and practices developed by CRAFT-OA remain relevant, visible, and usable beyond the project's lifetime.

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5.2 List of Websites

CRAFT-OA, <https://craft-oa.eu>

CRAFT-OA Blog, [CRAFT-OA Blog – CRAFT-OA](#)

DDH, [Home | Diamond Discovery Hub](#)

DIAMAS, <https://diamas.eu>

EDCH, [Home | EDCH](#)

EOSC, <https://eosc.eu>

OpenAIRE, <https://openaire.eu>

Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org>

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